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EFFECTS OF ULTRASOUND ON PULP BLEACHING

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Abstract

Ultrasound is the name given to the high frequency sound waves which the human ear cannot hear. Sound is a type of acoustic energy as a result of vibration. Sound is also defined as in form of a mechanical wave transport of energy into solid, liquid and gas environments.

The aim of this study is to improve physical and optical properties of chemi-thermomechanical pulp (CTMP) which has low brightness and strong tendency towards aging. For this reason, 6 different set of single stage applied and not applied pre-ultrasonic energy and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) bleaching operations were performed to CTMP produced from red pine (*Pinus brutia* ten.).

As the obtained results showed that, optical properties of CTMP were increased by applying pre-ultrasonic energy. Also, CTMP can be easily bleached with pre-ultrasonic energy. On the other hand, physical properties were also increased due to beating effects of ultrasonic energy on fibers. Brightness of bleached CTMP were increased from 42.61 to 66.62 while yellowness were decreased from 38.19 to 17.07 with using pre-ultrasonic energy.

Keywords: *Ultrasound, pulp, paper, bleaching, peroxide*

Introduction

The aim in the bleaching process is to modify or remove the lignin, extractive substances, metal ions and coloring agents from pulp by using chemicals (İmamoğlu, 2002).

High yield and low cost mechanical pulp is used in the manufacture of cheap and short life papers and paper boards. For this reason, mechanical pulp is used without bleaching or after one or two stage bleaching. The use of mechanical pulps is limited because of their insufficient brightness and rapid color reversion. To extend its usage for different paper grades it is necessary to bleach mechanical pulps (Tutuş and Usta, 2004; Usta and Tutuş, 1999).

Thermomechanical pulp (TMP) and chemi-thermomechanical pulp (CTMP) are widely used in the manufacture of newspaper. However, during last years

these pulps are increasingly preferred in the manufacture of lightweight coated papers and sanitary papers (Gagne et al., 1988).

By using peroxide in the bleaching process, paper's aging becomes slower, paper's cleaning gets easier, amount of resin decreases and the fibers become more elastic (Rudra and Bjorn, 1979; Usta and Tutuş, 1999).

Ultrasound is named for the oscillating sound pressure wave with a frequency greater than the upper limit of the human hearing range. When it hits a material, one part of it passes through the material and one part of it reflects back and one part of it is swallowed inside that material (Suslick, 1989).

The objective of the study is to investigate effects of ultrasound on CTMP pulp bleaching. For this reason, 6 different set of single stage applied (CTMP/Ult-P) and not applied (CTMP/P) pre-ultrasonic energy and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) bleaching operations were performed to CTMP. To this end, optical and physical properties of CTMP were determined.

Material and Method

Material

CTMP pulps used in this study were taken from SEKA Balıkesir pulp and paper mill. CTMP pulp whiteness, brightness, yellowness, opacity, breaking length, burst and tear index of the pulp were 58.86 ISO, 42.61 ISO, 38.19 E313, 97.24 ISO, 1090 meter, 0.50 kPa.m²/g, 0.81 mNm²/g, respectively.

Method

Before bleaching, 24000 Hz pre-ultrasonic energy was applied to the individualized CTMP in 3% concentration.

After being prepared bleaching liquors quantities shown Table 1, they were placed in polyethylene bags. Then, the mixtures were put in a circulation water bath and the temperature was controlled by a thermostat. At the end of bleaching the pulp was pressed up to 20-25% dryness. Later on, moisture content of pulps regulated to 20-25% and

placed in polyethylene bags and moisture content was determined.

Table 1. Bleaching conditions

H ₂ O ₂ ratio (comparing to the full dry pulp) (%)	: 3, 5, 7
Time (minute)	: 60
Temperature (°C)	: 75
EDTA ratio (%)	: 0.5
MgSO ₄ ratio (%)	: 0.5
Na ₂ SiO ₃ ratio (%)	: 3
Concentration (%)	: 12

* In this stage ratios are taken as; H₂O₂/NaOH ratio: 0.75; NaOH ratio: 9.33%, 6.66% and 4%

Handsheets of bleached pulps with grammage of 70 g/m² were prepared according to Tappi T 272 om-92 and made on a Rapid Kothen machine. Physical and optical properties of handsheets were measured according to Tappi Standart Test Methods given below.

- Breaking Length: H.E Messmer, Testometric 220M (Anonymous, 1992)
- Tear Index: Elmendorf Tearing Tester (Anonymous, 1992)
- Burst Index: B.F. Perkins & Son, Mullen Tester (Anonymous, 1992)
- Brightness, Whiteness, Yellowness and Opacity: Datacolor Elrepho (Anonymous, 1997)

Result and Discussion

Optical properties of the papers produced from the CTMP bleaching in this study are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Physical properties of papers produced from CTMP/P and CTMP/Ult-P.

	Whiteness (ISO)	Brightness (ISO)	Yellowness (E313)	Opacity (ISO)
Control	58.86	42.61	38.19	97.24
%3 P	74.40	61.79	21.80	93.11
%5 P	75.22	64.03	19.13	92.98
%7 P	76.11	65.25	17.18	92.06
Ultrasound	59.38	43.05	37.37	96.87
%3 Ult-P	75.47	62.70	21.38	92.30
%5 Ult-P	76.71	64.56	18.95	91.48
%7 Ult-P	77.65	66.62	17.07	90.41

In Table 2, when comparing not applied pre-ultrasonic energy (CTMP/P) with applied pre-ultrasonic energy (CTMP/Ult-P), it is observed that improving optical properties on CTMP/Ult-P. In a study, it is determined that ultrasonic treatment has an increase on the paper's optical properties (Karahana 2012).

Physical properties of the papers produced from the CTMP/P and CTMP/Ult-P bleaching are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Physical properties of papers produced from CTMP/P and CTMP/Ult-P

	Schopper Degree	Breaking Length	Burst Index (kPa.m ² /g)	Tear Index (mNm ² /g)
Control	20	1090	0.50	0.81
%3 P	22	1661	0.74	1.16
%5 P	23	1968	0.93	1.15
%7 P	24	2456	1.17	1.34
Ultrasound	22	1562	0.71	1.06
%3 Ult-P	23	1727	0.68	1.22
%5 Ult-P	24	1996	0.92	1.15
%7 Ult-P	25	2562	1.19	1.37

	(SR ^o)	(m)		
Control	20	1090	0.50	0.81
%3 P	22	1661	0.74	1.16
%5 P	23	1968	0.93	1.15
%7 P	24	2456	1.17	1.34
Ultrasound	22	1562	0.71	1.06
%3 Ult-P	23	1727	0.68	1.22
%5 Ult-P	24	1996	0.92	1.15
%7 Ult-P	25	2562	1.19	1.37

In Table 3, it was determined that physical properties of the papers produced from CTMP/Ult-P are higher than CTMP/P.

In one study, it was concluded that ultrasonic treatment increases the quality of papers (Tatsumi et al, 2000). In another study, it was determined that after ultrasonic treatment there is an increase in paper quality and it shows a more environmentalist attitude (Brouderand and Gerhardstein, 1998).

Pre-ultrasonic treatment has a beating effect on the fibers and there is an increase in physical properties because of increasing bonds between fibers.

The results show that CTMP can be bleached to 66.62 (ISO) brightness and 17.07 (E313) yellowness with pre-ultrasonic energy and peroxide bleaching. It was found that physical properties of CTMP/Ult-P bleached pulps were better than CTMP/P. According to the results CTMP/Ult-P offers the following advantages;

1. Easier cleaning, because dark spots in the pulp diminish 35-40% during bleaching.
2. Less aging tendency of peroxide bleached pulps.
3. Dust amount decreases in the paper production due to increased fiber-fiber bond.
4. Peroxide bleaching provides to reduce resin content with using ultrasonic energy.
5. CTMP can be easily bleached with applying pre-ultrasonic energy.
6. Ultrasonic energy provides an increase in physical properties due to beating effect on the fibers depend on schopper degree (SR^o).
7. Pre-ultrasonic treatment provides chemicals to be penetrated much easier on the fibers. Thus, with fewer chemicals, intended optical and physical properties can be reached.
8. Printing and writing properties of CTMP/Ult-P improve.
9. During the paper production there are raises in retention because of increased bonds between fibers.
10. Embossing of tissue paper is easier with CTMP/Ult-P pulps.

As a result of all these advantages, CTMP/Ult-P provides economic and technical possibilities. Besides, CTMP/Ult-P can be used in newspaper manufacture as well as in high quality printing and writing papers as a mixture of sulfate and sulfite pulps.

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